

Synthesis and spectroscopic studies of transition metal complexes with 1,5:10,14-dimetheno-[1,4,8,11]-tetraazatetradeca-1,3,5,6,8,10,12,14,15,17-decane a fourteen membered tetradentate macrocyclic ligand

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Abstract : Complexes of Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pd^{II}, Pt^{II}, Ru^{II} and Ir^{II} with a fourteen membered 1,5:10,14-dimetheno-[1,4,8,11]-tetraazatetradeca-1,3,5,6,8,10,12,14,15,17-decane macrocyclic ligand have been synthesized. These complexes have been characterized by magnetic moment, IR, electronic, EPR and Mössbauer spectral studies. All of complexes were found to have six coordinated octahedral geometry and are of high-spin type, except the Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes which are four coordinate, square planar and diamagnetic.

Keywords : Macrocyclic ligand, transition metal ions, tetradentate ligand.

Transition metal complexes of synthetic macrocyclic ligands are of significance because porphyrins and cobalamines play vital roles in biological systems. Such chelating molecules are important since they are capable of furnishing an environment of controlled geometry and ligand field strength. Synthetic macrocycles are a growing class of compound with varying chemistry with a wide range of different molecular topologies and set of donor atoms¹. In the present paper we report the synthesis and characterization of Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Pd^{II}, Pt^{II}, Ru^{II} and Ir^{II} complexes of 1,5:10,14-dimetheno-[1,4,8,11]-tetraazatetradeca-1,3,5,6,8,10,12,14,15,17-decane macrocyclic ligand (GMP) :

Structure of the ligand GMP

Results and discussion

The analytical and molar conductance (Table 1) values of all the complexes in DMF solution suggest that general formula of the complexes are $[M^1LCl_2]$ [where $M^1 = Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}$ and $L = GMP$], $[M^2LCl_2]Cl$

[where $M^2 = Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Ru^{III}$ and Ir^{III}] and $[M^3L]Cl_2$ [where $M^3 = Pd^{II}, Pt^{II}$]. IR spectra of the complexes do not show any band corresponding to either primary diamine or free keto group. It indicates that there is a complete condensation of amino group with keto group. A new band in the complexes appears at 1620 cm^{-1} , it may be due to $\nu C=N$ group. These ligands coordinated to the metal through nitrogen of $C=N$ group². Therefore, ligand acts as tetradentate. Absorption in the range $700\text{--}780$ and $1400\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to phenyl group. The band appearing around 450 cm^{-1} in all the complexes indicates $\nu M-N$ vibration, which further confirms the coordination of these groups with metal ions.

At room temperature the magnetic moment of the chromium complex is 3.72 B.M., as expected for high-spin octahedral complex. The electronic spectrum of the complex recorded in DMF displays two bands at 18300 and 22250 cm^{-1} , corresponding to spin allowed transitions $^4A_{2g} \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}(F)$ and $^4A_{2g} \rightarrow ^4T_{1g}(P)$ respectively. Various ligand field parameters have been calculated and are presented in Table 2. The EPR spectrum of the polycrystalline sample has been recorded at room temperature. The g value is found to be 1.89.

The manganese(II) complex shows a magnetic moment corresponding to five unpaired electrons (5.98 B.M.) which indicates that Mn^{II} complex is in high-spin. The electronic spectrum of the complex displays weak absorption bands at $18050, 24650, 29550$ and 31750 cm^{-1}

Table 1. Molar conductance and elemental analysis of complexes

Sl. no.	Complex and imperial formula	Mol. conductance ^a ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Colour	Yield (%)	M.p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Elemental analysis (%) :			
						Found (Calcd.)			
						M	C	H	N
1.	Cr(GMP)Cl ₃	95.0	Brown	60	220	12.20	45.08	2.68	13.29
	Cr(C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄)Cl ₃					(12.42)	(45.87)	(2.86)	(13.38)
2.	Mn(GMP)Cl ₂	9.9	Brown	55	225	14.02	49.64	2.82	13.93
	Mn(C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄)Cl ₂					(14.24)	(49.74)	(3.10)	(14.51)
3.	Fe(GMP)Cl ₃	112.0	Black	62	225	13.73	45.24	1.99	12.39
	Fe(C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄)Cl ₂					(13.22)	(45.46)	(2.84)	(13.26)
4.	Co(GMP)Cl ₂	13.1	Black	65	238	15.36	49.28	2.67	14.14
	Co(C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄)Cl ₂					(15.11)	(49.23)	(3.07)	(14.36)
5.	Ni(GMP)Cl ₂	8.2	Dark brown	55	237	14.50	48.74	2.74	14.49
	Ni(C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄)Cl ₂					(15.07)	(48.27)	(3.08)	(14.37)
6.	Cu(GMP)Cl ₂	15.5	Black	62	225	15.94	48.42	2.15	13.61
	Cu(C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄)Cl ₂					(16.11)	(48.66)	(3.04)	(14.19)
7.	Ru(GMP)Cl ₃	88.7	Black	58	239	21.07	40.95	2.92	11.09
	Ru(C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄)Cl ₃					(21.60)	(41.07)	(2.56)	(11.98)
8.	Pd(GMP)Cl ₂	249.0	Greenish brown	50	244	24.12	43.45	5.08	12.31
	Pd(C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄)Cl ₂					(24.26)	(43.94)	(5.49)	(12.82)
9.	Pt(GMP)Cl ₂	250.0	Black	52	243	37.35	36.14	2.13	10.05
	Pt(C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄)Cl ₂					(37.07)	(36.50)	(2.28)	(10.65)
10.	Ir(GMP)Cl ₃	109.0	Black	59	250	33.79	33.13	2.03	9.76
	Ir(C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₄)Cl ₃					(34.38)	(34.38)	(2.15)	(10.03)

^aSolvent used for molar conductance : DMF.

Table 2. Ligand field parameters of the complexes

Complex	Dq (cm^{-1})	B (cm^{-1})	β	C (cm^{-1})	Z	LFSE (kJ mol^{-1})	g	F_4	F_2	h_x
Cr(GMP)Cl ₃	1830	353	0.38	1414	0.64	262.7	1.89	-	-	-
Mn(GMP)Cl ₂	1805	700	0.89	3530	-	-	1.99	101	1205	1.57
Co(GMP)Cl ₂	1402	1085	0.96	-	-	223.9	-	-	-	-
Ni(GMP)Cl ₂	1070	603	0.58	2412	-	153.4	-	-	-	-

characteristic of octahedral geometry. These bands may be assigned to : ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} ({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_{1g}$, ${}^4A_{1g} ({}^4G)$, ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g ({}^4D)$ and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g} ({}^4P)$ transitions, respectively. The value for the ligand field parameters have been determined and are listed in Table 2. Parameters B and C are calculated by using the methods as reported earlier³. The calculated value of β indicates that the complex under study has covalent character. The EPR spectrum of the complex has been recorded as polycrystalline sample and in DMF solution. The polycrystalline sample gives one broad isotropic signal centered approx free electron g -value i.e. 2.0023. The broadening of the spectrum may be due to the spin relaxation. In DMF

solution the complex gives an EPR spectrum containing six lines arising due to hyperfine interaction between the unpaired electrons and Mn nucleus ($I = 5/2$). The nuclear magnetic quantum number, MI corresponding to these lines are $-5/2, -3/2, -1/2, +1/2, +3/2$ and $+5/2$ low to high field.

Iron(III) complex have the composition of $[\text{FeLCl}_3]$ where L is the ligand. This complex also shows a magnetic moment of 5.98 B.M., indicating the presence of high-spin Fe^{III} ion. The electronic spectrum of this complex shows three spectral bands at 17000, 20000 and 25700 cm^{-1} which is characteristic of octahedral geometry. The Mössbauer spectral values [isomer shift =

0.7129 mm s⁻¹ at 300 K and quadrupole splitting value = 1.2345 mm s⁻¹] indicate that the iron exists in +3 oxidation state and have distorted octahedral geometry with four nitrogen and two chlorine atoms surrounding it.

The magnetic moment of cobalt(II) complex is 5.02 B.M. expected for high-spin complexes. The electronic spectrum exhibits a broad band at *ca.* 8750 cm⁻¹ and two shoulders at 14700 and 20700 cm⁻¹. These bands may be assigned to ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{2g}, ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴A_{2g}, ⁴T_{1g} → ⁴T_{1g} (*P*) transitions, respectively. The low value of $v_2/v_1 = 1.68$, may be due distortion of the octahedral structure⁴. This is consistent with very broad nature of v_1 band, which may be assigned to the envelope of transition from ⁴E_g (⁴T_{1g}) to the components ⁴B_{2g} and ⁴E_g of ⁴T_{2g} characteristic of tetragonally distorted octahedral environment. The EPR spectrum of the complex under study is recorded at liquid nitrogen temperature because of the rapid spin lattice relaxation of Co^{II} broadens the lines at higher temperature, $g_{||} = 5.871$ and $g_{\perp} = 3.067$. The large deviation of *g* values from the spin only value ($g = 2.0023$) is due to large angular momentum contribution.

Nickel(II) complex shows a magnetic moment (2.95 B.M.) corresponding to two unpaired electrons. The electronic spectrum of the Ni^{II} complex shows two well defined bands at 10700 and 16450 cm⁻¹ assignable to ³A_{2g} → ³T_{2g} (*F*) and ³A_{2g} → ³T_{1g} (*F*) transitions, respectively. Here splitting of the v_1 band is not observed, which generally observed in *D*_{4h} symmetry. So *D*_t, *Dq*^E and *Dq*^A can not be calculated. The third *d-d* transition band (v_3) which may be obscured by the more intense charge transfer band, is calculated to be at 24700 cm⁻¹. The value of the v_2/v_1 is 1.54 and the ligand field parameters *Dq*, *B* and β have been found to be 1070 cm⁻¹, 603 cm⁻¹ and 0.58, respectively. All of these values, together with the magnetic moment (2.95 B.M.) are characteristic of an octahedral geometry of this complex.

The magnetic moment of the copper(II) complex is 1.95 B.M. The electronic spectrum of six coordinate Cu^{II} complex have either *D*_{4h} or *C*_{4v} symmetry and the E_g and T_{2g} levels of the ²D free ion will split into B_{1g}, A_{1g}, B_{2g} and E_{1g} levels, respectively. Thus, three spin allowed transitions are expected in the visible or near IR region. But only few complexes are known, in which such bands are resolved either by "Gaussian analysis" or by single crystal polarization studies⁴. These bands have been assigned to the following transitions, in order of increasing energy ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g}, ²B_{1g} → ²B_{2g} and ²B_{1g} → ²E_g. The electronic spectrum of the complex shows bands at 13400

cm⁻¹ and a well-defined shoulder at 18650 cm⁻¹. These may be assigned to the ²B_{1g} → ²A_{1g} and ²B_{1g} → ²E_g transitions, respectively. The EPR spectrum⁵ of the present complex exhibits a well resolved anisotropic signal in the parallel and perpendicular ⁶³Cu region. The *g* values are calculated and found $g_{||} 2.2755$ and $g_{\perp} 2.0680$, which are closer to 2. The trend $g_{||} > g_{\perp}$ is observed in these complexes. This suggests major distortion in Cu^{II} complex from *Oh* symmetry i.e. *D*_{4h} symmetry.

Palladium(II) complex is diamagnetic as expected for a low-spin *d*⁸ system. The low-spin square planar metal complexes are characterized by three spin allowed *d-d* bands, corresponding to the ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g}, ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_g and ¹A_g → ¹E_g transitions, respectively. The complex under study display two bands at 24870 and 28550 cm⁻¹. These bands may be assigned to ¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹B_g transitions, respectively.

Iridium(III) complex is diamagnetic as expected. Electronic spectrum of the complex positively affirms an octahedral configuration around the central metal ion. Electronic spectrum displays bands at 17550, 23250 and at 38025 cm⁻¹. The first two bands may be assigned to ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{1g} and ¹A_{1g} → ¹T_{2g} transitions in increasing order of energy. The third band at 38025 cm⁻¹, may be due to charge transfer.

Ru^{III} complex shows magnetic moment 1.70 B.M. at room temperature, which is lower than the spin only value. The lowering in μ_{eff} value may arise due to effect of ligand field, metal-metal interaction or considerable electron delocalization. The electronic spectrum of the complex shows an octahedral configuration around the central metal ion. The electronic spectral bands appear at 13750, 17275, 25125 cm⁻¹ and a few bands above 30000 cm⁻¹ in Ru^{III} complexes. These bands may be assigned to ²T_{2g} → ⁴T_{1g}, ²T_{2g} → ⁴T_{2g} and ²T_{2g} → ²A_{2g} transitions, respectively in order of increasing energy. The bands above 30000 cm⁻¹ may be due to charge transfer. The ligand field parameters Δ , *B* and β have been calculated for the complex and are listed in Table 2. The values of Δ , *B* and β and v_1/v_2 are zero, 491 cm⁻¹, 0.78 and 1.25 respectively. The value of β indicates that there is considerable covalency in the metal ligand σ bond.

Platinum(II) complex is diamagnetic, which indicates that this complex has the square planar geometry. The electronic spectra of the complex positively affirm the presence of square planar geometry of the complex. Three *d-d* spin allowed transitions are expected corresponding to the transitions from three lower lying "*d*" levels to the empty *d*_{x²-y² orbital. The ground state is ¹A_{1g} and the}

excited states corresponding to these transitions are ${}^1A_{2g}$, ${}^1B_{1g}$ and 1E_g in increasing order of energy. Electronic spectrum displays bands at 24870 and 28550 and 40980 cm^{-1} . These bands may be assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transitions respectively. Third band may be due to charge transfer.

On the basis of spectral studies following octahedral structures may be suggested for the complexes.

$M^I = \text{Cr}^{III}, \text{Fe}^{III}, \text{Ru}^{III} \text{ and } \text{Ir}^{III}$

$M^{II} = \text{Mn}^{II}, \text{Co}^{II}, \text{Ni}^{II} \text{ and } \text{Cu}^{II}$

$M^{III} = \text{Pd}^{II} \text{ and } \text{Pt}^{II}$

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade and were procured from Aldrich. Metal salts were purchased from E. Merck and were used as received. All solvents used were of spectroscopic grade.

A template reaction was carried out for the synthesis

of the complexes. A hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of the metal chloride (0.025 mol) was mixed with a hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of *m*-phenylenediamine (0.05 mol) and an ethanolic solution (20 mL) of glyoxal (0.05 mol) in the presence of a few drops of conc. HCl. The solution was refluxed for four to five hours in each case. On cooling the reaction mixture overnight, the complexes precipitated out. They were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried over P_4O_{10} , yield : 49–68%.

Microanalysis (C, H and N) of these complexes were carried out on a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 instrument as Nujol mulls [for 1 and 7] and in KBr pellets [for 2,3,4,5,6,8,9 and 10]. Electronic spectra were recorded in DMF solution on a Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer. The molar conductance was measured on an Elico conductivity bridge (type CM₈2T) and magnetic susceptibility was measured on Gouy-balance at room temperature by using $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as celebrant. EPR spectra of the complexes were recorded as polycrystalline sample at room temperature on an E-4 EPR spectrometer, using DPPH as g-marker. The molecular weight of complexes were determined cryscopically in benzene.

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